

EDUCATION SYSTEM IN PRIMARY GRADES**Berdybaeva Gulziya Jenisbaevna**

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Abstract: As you know, life is reflected through images in a work of art. At its center is man, his relationship to nature and society. The rules of depicting existence and reality in the work of art with the help of images, providing objective content and subjective assessment in concrete material are of great theoretical and practical importance for the methodology.

Key words: elementary, reading book, text, pedagogue, student, work, incident.

According to psychologists, it is not enough to understand a work of art to understand it. Perception of a work is a complex process, which involves the emergence of some kind of attitude towards the work and the reality depicted in it. Young students have two different attitudes towards the literary hero.

Students use their personal understanding to evaluate the characters participating in the play. They lack vocabulary and experience to evaluate other qualities of the hero. The task of the teacher is to show the qualities that the students did not notice and to introduce them into the speech of the students. It is worth paying attention to one more thing:

1. Students do not take into account the circumstances in which they act when expressing their relationship to the hero of the work.
2. They can't understand why the hero has to do this, they need to act accordingly.

Working on a work of art is a complex process, and the educational tasks of the teacher's reading classes require taking into account the specific characteristics of the work of art and the readiness of students.

All components are interconnected in a work of art. The characters develop in the play. As the events develop, new aspects of the characters are revealed. These

features require a comprehensive reading, perception, that is, synthesis, while working on the work. After reading the work from the beginning to the end, it is analyzed, and then it goes to a high-quality synthesis. Before starting to read the work, it is necessary to prepare students for reading the work of art. So, the preparatory period gives the process of synthesis-analysis-synthesis.

In order for students to understand the content of the work correctly, it is necessary to have a certain idea about life. Preparations are being made for this.

Tasks of preparatory work:

1. To enrich students' imaginations about the events depicted in the work, to provide new information that affects the conscious perception of the text, to create conditions for students to be able to connect the facts described in the work of art with their observations in their lives.
2. Introducing the writer's life, arousing interest in the writer, his life and work.
3. Preparing students for emotional perception of the work.

It is important for the teacher to solve the following issues of the process of working on an artistic work during the reading activity. These begin with determining the purpose and content of working on the work. The content of work on the work is determined based on the mental state of the students in the class, the situation and situations among the students of the class. The next task is to determine the lesson steps for the analysis of the work. This task depends on the methodical preparation of the teacher for the lesson process, on the basis of which methods he organizes and manages the lesson process. It is important for the teacher to develop a system of tasks for the analysis of each work while working on an artistic work.

The next issue is the task of determining the range of knowledge, skills and abilities that students will acquire. In the process of working on a work of art, attention is paid to the students' thinking, their ability to express their thoughts in speech, and how they can manifest themselves at any stage of work on the work of art.

Work on a work of art in elementary grades is divided into three main stages:

1. The first stage of synthesis. The main task of this stage is to introduce the exact content of the work and visual means of expression based on the overall perception of the text. First of all, the teacher chooses the method that is convenient for him in order to bring the work to the attention of the students. For example, a teacher's story, an audio form of the text of the work, a film screening, a role-playing reading of the work by several students, etc. In this case, the type of work is chosen in accordance with the characteristics of the work of art and in which class it is taught. At the beginning of this stage, the teacher should also provide information about the author of the work.

2. Analysis stage. The task of this stage is to determine the connection of the development of events in the artistic work, the behavior of the participating persons (How did he behave? Why did he do this?) and to reveal their main characteristics (focus on the positive and negative characteristics of the characters), the work opening its composition (node, culminating point, solution), analyzing the specific content of the work together with visual means, that is, vividly depicting what is depicted in the work of art, artistic images and means of expression that serve to vividly express feelings and experiences, imagery (imagery) and attention to elements that enhance emotionality and evaluation of the characters' behavior (what the author described, how he described it, why he chose this or that evidence).

In primary grades, the task of teaching correct, fast, conscious and expressive reading is carried out along with the formation of the ability to analyze the work in students. The relationship between the formation of reading skills and working on the text determines how to approach the analysis of the work.

The 2nd stage of working on a work of art is the analysis of the work. The main direction of the analysis of the work is to determine the exact content of the text (events and its development), composition, morals and character traits of the

participating persons, the idea of the work.

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